

The social cost of chronic health conditions and their potential for rehabilitation towards an aging population

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Paper 1

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Paper 2

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²<https://veluxstiftung.ch/projects/new-perspectives-for-healthy-ageing/>

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Background and Motivation

The population aging imposes several challenges and opportunities for the organization of health and social systems. As people live longer and often in better health, they can remain active in the workforce and contribute to society beyond traditional retirement ages [1]. However, at the same time, this demographic shift is also characterized by a rising prevalence of chronic conditions, which is currently the leading cause of disability [2]. Globally, chronic conditions such as ischemic heart disease, stroke, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) are not only the main causes of death, but also the drivers of disability adjusted years (DALYs) worldwide [3, 4, 5].

Extensive literature exists studying how specific chronic conditions impact individuals, as well as the effects on the costs for the healthcare system. [6, 7]. However, their economic burden extends beyond that due to its long-term nature. In fact, chronic conditions reduce the intrinsic capacity of people with important implications for their activity and participation, being the most worrisome the effects in the labor market. Several studies have shown how people with chronic conditions have higher rates of absenteeism [8], increasing demand for disability benefits or early retirement [9]. In addition, chronic conditions are associated with higher levels of healthcare utilization. These results are particularly pronounced among vulnerable populations, where poverty, limited education,

and restricted access to care can exacerbate adverse health and economic outcomes [10].

To quantify these impacts, the literature has commonly adopted the cost-of-illness (COI) approach, which considers direct and indirect costs [11]. *Direct costs* are related to the treatment of the chronic condition, which includes costs such as hospitalization and medical care. *Indirect costs* arise from the effects of the chronic disease, and include productivity losses, dependence on others, among others. Several studies have estimated these costs for specific conditions including diabetes [12], stroke [13], chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) [14], arthritis [15], mental health disorders [16], kidney disease [17], and cancer [18]. Despite this growing attention, existing studies mostly offer condition specific results, mostly describing correlations, which limits to capture the cumulative effects of chronic conditions. This fragmented effect makes it harder to develop clear and effective public policies that deal with chronic conditions in a comprehensive and lasting way. Moreover, few studies explore potential solutions from the health system perspective, such as preventive or rehabilitative care, to mitigate the effects of these conditions [19].

While prevention is a long-term goal, it does not address the existing and growing population already living with chronic conditions. For this group, the sole health strategy that targets people's functioning is rehabilitation[20]. Rehabilitation, defined as the set of interventions designed to optimize functioning and reduce disability, can help people with chronic conditions to remain independent for as long as possible, with important implications for society.

This thesis aims to close this gap and contributes to the literature by providing a comprehensive assessment of the economic burden of chronic conditions in 9 European countries. It focuses on both direct and indirect costs and explores the underused but promising role of rehabilitation. Specifically, it estimates the impact of chronic conditions on healthcare utilization (direct costs) and labor market participation (indirect costs), and it evaluates the effectiveness and efficiency of rehabilitation using an extreme case of disability, like spinal cord injury (SCI) as a case study.

In addition, this thesis implements an innovative methodological framework, using

causal inference for panel data. We apply difference-in-differences models with multiple time periods to study how the diagnosis of a chronic condition impacts the utilization of healthcare services and the productivity of individuals. I combine these estimates with unit costs of healthcare services (WHO-CHOICE) and concepts from insurance mathematics to quantify the healthcare cost burden. Finally, using real world data, I show how rehabilitation can be an effective strategy to improve independence measures of patients with high level of disability.

1.1 Research Objectives and Structure

The objective of this thesis is to quantify the effect of chronic conditions on healthcare costs and the labor market. Also, to evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of rehabilitation in keeping people independent. This is achieved through the following studies:

- Study 1: Chronic conditions and their impact on healthcare utilization and costs.
Aim: To estimate the additional use of health services due to chronic conditions and its cost.
- Study 2: Chronic conditions and their impact in the labor market.
Aim: To estimate the productivity losses due to chronic conditions, assessing their impact on the participation and economic burden in the labor market.
- Study 3: Efficiency and effectiveness of rehabilitation for persons with spinal cord injury (SCI).
Aim: To estimate how rehabilitation improves functional independence of persons with paraplegia/tetraplegia.

1.2 Data Sources and Methodological Approach

This thesis is fed with data from several sources. First, it analyzed data from the Survey on Health, Aging and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)[21]. SHARE is a longitudinal

data set that covers European countries. The data contain information on health conditions, utilization of healthcare care services, and socioeconomic factors in people 50+ years of age. Second, I use the WHO-CHOICE data set. This program, developed by the World Health Organization (WHO), provides evidence on the unit costs of inpatient and outpatient care at country level . Finally, for the third study, in which we analyze the role of rehabilitation and disability, we have considered routine clinical data from patients with SCI who received rehabilitation from Swiss Paraplegic Center, one of the four specialized SCI rehabilitation centers in Switzerland.

To analyze the effect of chronic conditions on productivity and use of healthcare services, we consider the potential outcomes framework [22],[23] (Rubin’s causal model). This framework identifies causal effects by comparing the outcomes that an individual would experience with and without a treatment, which in the case of this thesis is the diagnosis of a chronic condition. For each individual in the survey, we have two potential outcomes, but only one is observed. Causal inference then involves estimating the missing counterfactual using a synthetic control group.

The outcomes analyzed were the number of working hours in the last week (Study 1) and the number of doctor visits and overnight hospital stays (Study 2). To estimate causal effects in this setting, I implemented the Callaway and Sant’Anna difference in difference estimator [24], which is specifically designed for multiple time periods with the adoption of staggered treatment. This approach allows to make comparisons between treated and untreated individuals over time, providing estimates of the average effect of treatment.

For the last study, I employed generalized additive models (GAMs) to estimate the effectiveness and efficiency of specialized rehabilitation. The outcome measured in this model, was the independence metric (SCIM III), which is a standard measure collected in clinical settings. GAMs account for the nonlinear relationship between rehabilitation and functional independence, particularly with respect to length of stay and costs. This modeling choice was supported by related evidence on the nonlinear association between healthcare spending and health outcomes, which typically relies on aggregate health ex-

penditure data [25].

In contrast, our study focused on spinal cord injury (SCI), a condition that, due to its complexity and intensive resource needs, serves as a tracer condition to evaluate the performance of health systems [26].

SCI becomes highly relevant not only because of its profound and life-changing impact on individuals, but also because it involves an initial period of acute hospitalization followed by a lengthy process of rehabilitation and adaptation to a new way of life [27]. Importantly, SCI care requires a broad range of health services across sectors, offering valuable insights into the functioning of the healthcare system. In this study, we focus on Switzerland, as it provides detailed individual-level data on rehabilitation and service use, which aligns with the overall objectives of the thesis.

Chapter 2

Excess Healthcare Utilization and Costs

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Chapter 3

Chronic Diseases and Labor Market Impact

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Chapter 4

Rehabilitation Efficiency and Effectiveness

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Chapter 5

Discussion and Conclusion

5.1 Main Findings

This thesis provides evidence on the economic impact of chronic conditions, both in terms of direct costs or excess healthcare utilization, and indirect costs or productivity losses. In this thesis, I also highlight the potential of rehabilitation as a health strategy to mitigate these costs by the improvement of functional outcomes.

5.1.1 Chronic conditions and healthcare utilization

This thesis shows that chronic diseases are associated with a significant increase in healthcare service utilization. On average, individuals diagnosed with a chronic disease reported up to four additional outpatient visits per year in Germany, Belgium, and Austria, three extra visits in Italy, Spain, Switzerland, France, and Denmark; and one in Sweden. On the other hand, for inpatient care, Switzerland and Austria observe an average of two additional overnight stays, followed by Germany, Belgium, and France with one, and less than one in Spain, Italy, and Sweden. Denmark shows no significant effects.

While chronic diseases lead to increased use in both outpatient and inpatient care, the financial burden is concentrated in inpatient services. Austria and Switzerland report the highest inpatient cost burdens, reaching up to 12.8% and 8.6% of total health expenditure, respectively. These findings indicate that inpatient services remain the most expensive component of the healthcare costs associated with chronic conditions.

There are also clear differences between countries in healthcare utilization. Germany, Belgium, and Austria had the highest increases in outpatient visits (up to 4 extra per year), while Sweden had only one. For inpatient care, Switzerland and Austria showed the largest effects with about two extra overnight stays per year. In contrast, Denmark showed no significant change. These differences also appear in costs with Austria and Switzerland having the highest inpatient cost burden, while Sweden and Denmark had the lowest.

5.1.2 Chronic conditions and the labor market

Individuals facing chronic diseases significantly reduce labor market participation. Applying a difference-in-differences approach with multiple time periods, the results reveal that people diagnosed with a chronic condition consistently work fewer hours compared to their healthy counterparts. On average, men reduced their working time by 6.78 hours per week (a 14% decrease), and women by 3.97 hours (13%). This reduction translates into considerable productivity losses across countries, estimated at approximately USD 12.8 billion annually. The conditions with the largest negative impacts include heart attack, stroke, and chronic lung disease. These findings underscore the substantial economic cost of chronic conditions, especially in aging populations, and the need for targeted interventions to protect work capacity and mitigate long-term disability.

The estimated effect varies across countries. Belgium and Germany showed the largest drops in working hours, with up to 8 hours less per week for men in Belgium, while Italy and Sweden had smaller reductions. In monetary terms, Denmark and Belgium had the highest productivity losses, reaching over 10% of their total health spending. These differences reflect how disease burden differs between countries.

5.1.3 Rehabilitation improves functional recovery and mitigate economic consequences

Finally, in this thesis we also provide evidence for rehabilitation interventions, particularly in the case of spinal cord injury (SCI). Rehabilitation can significantly improve patient functional independence. On average, patients with SCI improved their SCIM score by 36 points during the (sub)acute phase of rehabilitation. This recovery potential varied according to the level of injury,

age and comorbidities, with less severe injuries showing higher gains and greater efficiency. However, even among the most severe injuries, functional improvements were observed.

These findings suggest that rehabilitation not only improves functioning, which can contribute to reducing future healthcare use and to facilitate return to work or social participation by mitigating both direct healthcare costs and productivity losses. Therefore, optimization of rehabilitation services and the implementation of customized interventions based on patient characteristics play an important role in the management of the future economic consequences of chronic diseases.

5.2 Limitations and Future Research

This thesis provides new evidence on the economic consequences of chronic conditions and the potential of rehabilitation to mitigate its impacts. However, several limitations should be acknowledged.

First, the analyzes were based on secondary data sources, which can present some restrictions. The SHARE dataset, while highly valuable for cross-country comparisons, is based on self-reported information for chronic diseases and utilization of healthcare, which may introduce some bias. In addition, the available data limit the measurement of certain aspects such as disease severity, informal care, outpatient rehabilitation use, or adaptations to work, which could all play an important role in the economic consequences of chronic diseases.

Second, the estimate of healthcare costs was based on unit costs from WHO-CHOICE from 15 years ago, which, although standardized and comparable between countries, may not fully capture local price variations, heterogeneity in healthcare markets, or out-of-pocket expenditures. Similarly, the estimation of productivity losses was based on minimum and average wage levels and did not account for variations in income, informal work, or wealth effects.

Third, the results of the rehabilitation analysis are specific to Switzerland and the inpatient rehabilitation phase. These findings provide valuable information on the effectiveness and efficiency of rehabilitation for spinal cord injury (SCI) patients, but they may not apply to other countries or to the post-acute rehabilitation phase, where long-term outcomes and community reintegration is more relevant.

Finally, the analysis of labor market results was limited to individuals 50+ years of age and

older, given the structure of the SHARE data. This excludes the potential economic consequences of chronic conditions for younger populations of working age, who may face different labor market dynamics.

5.2.1 Future Research Directions

Future research could build on this work in several directions. First, it is necessary to examine long-term patient trajectories after rehabilitation, to better understand whether functional improvements translate into sustained independence, return to work, and reduced use of healthcare over time. Second, expanding the cost analysis to include outpatient rehabilitation, long-term care, informal care, assistive devices, and home adaptations would allow a better evaluation of the economic consequences of chronic conditions and rehabilitation.

Third, future studies could integrate patient reported outcome measures (PROMs) and patient reported experience measures (PREMs) to capture broader dimensions of rehabilitation outcomes beyond functional improvement alone. Comparative research across different healthcare systems would also provide valuable insights into how organizational structures and financing models affect rehabilitation effectiveness, efficiency, and cost burden.

Finally, understanding the role of integrated care pathways combining primary care, outpatient services, and community based rehabilitation could offer important evidence to guide the development of efficient and tailored models of care for individuals with chronic diseases.

Future research should explore the effect of the increased healthcare utilization and productivity losses caused by chronic conditions affect the sustainability of social systems such as, health insurance, disability insurance, and pension schemes, all of them very relevant in the insurance industry context. Future studies could consider to model the total costs as the product of frequency and severity components, to capture the variability and uncertainty in the expenditure associated to chronic conditions. These models could be use stochastic simulation techniques to explore how rising chronic disease prevalence and increasing healthcare needs affect future healthcare costs. This approach could allow researchers and policymakers to explore future scenarios, test the resilience of current financing structures, and design strategies that protect the sustainability of social systems.

In this case rehabilitation also plays an important role, helping people become more independent and reducing their future need for care, it may lower long term healthcare costs. In this

context, a good understanding of rehabilitation effectiveness and efficiency is essential. Future simulations could test different scenarios of these metrics, for example, increasing or decreasing rehabilitation resources to see how these changes would affect patient outcomes and the financial pressure on insurance systems. This could help policymakers to plan how to invest in rehabilitation as a way to reduce the long-term impact of chronic diseases.

5.3 Conclusion

In conclusion, this thesis shows that chronic diseases have important economic consequences, both for individuals and health systems. People with chronic diseases use more healthcare services and face productivity losses, especially in the labor market. At the same time, the results show that rehabilitation can play a key role in helping people recover their independence. This is important not only for their health, but also because it can reduce future healthcare use and productivity losses. Investing in rehabilitation should be seen as part of the strategy to manage the economic impact of chronic conditions.

This thesis is one of the few studies to provide country level causal estimates on the economic impact of chronic diseases, including both healthcare utilization and productivity losses. These findings are very important evidence to support the design of policy interventions tailored to the specific characteristics of each country's health and social systems.

Bibliography

- [1] B Franklin. “Towards a longevity dividend: Life expectancy and productivity across developed countries”. In: *International Longevity Centre, United Kingdom, London* (2018).
- [2] Xiaodong Sun and Xuan Li. *Aging and chronic disease: public health challenge and education reform*. 2023.
- [3] World Health Organization. *The top 10 causes of death*. 2023. URL: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/the-top-10-causes-of-death> (visited on 06/12/2025).
- [4] Karen Hacker. “The burden of chronic disease”. In: *Mayo Clinic Proceedings: Innovations, Quality & Outcomes* 8.1 (2024), pp. 112–119.
- [5] Caroline S Blaum, Jersey Liang, and Xian Liu. “The relationship of chronic diseases and health status to the health services utilization of older Americans”. In: *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society* 42.10 (1994), pp. 1087–1093.
- [6] RM Leadley et al. “Chronic diseases in the European Union: the prevalence and health cost implications of chronic pain”. In: *Journal of pain & palliative care pharmacotherapy* 26.4 (2012), pp. 310–325.
- [7] Jelena Arsenijevic et al. “Catastrophic health care expenditure among older people with chronic diseases in 15 European countries”. In: *PloS one* 11.7 (2016), e0157765.
- [8] Kelli Destri et al. “Obesity-attributable costs of absenteeism among working adults in Portugal”. In: *BMC public health* 22.1 (2022), p. 978.

- [9] Tiziana Li Ranzi, Angelo d’Errico, and Giuseppe Costa. “Association between chronic morbidity and early retirement in Italy”. In: *International archives of occupational and environmental health* 86 (2013), pp. 295–303.
- [10] World Health Organization. *Social determinants of health*. 2023. URL: https://www.who.int/health-topics/social-determinants-of-health#tab=tab_1 (visited on 06/12/2025).
- [11] Changik Jo. “Cost-of-illness studies: concepts, scopes, and methods”. In: *Clinical and molecular hepatology* 20.4 (2014), p. 327.
- [12] Laura N McEwen and William H Herman. “Health care utilization and costs of diabetes”. In: (2021).
- [13] Stefan Strilciuc et al. “The economic burden of stroke: a systematic review of cost of illness studies”. In: *Journal of medicine and life* 14.5 (2021), p. 606.
- [14] Jeetvan G Patel, Saurabh P Nagar, and Anand A Dalal. “Indirect costs in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: a review of the economic burden on employers and individuals in the United States”. In: *International Journal of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease* (2014), pp. 289–300.
- [15] LC Franke et al. “Cost-of-illness of rheumatoid arthritis and ankylosing spondylitis”. In: *Clinical and experimental rheumatology* 27.4, Suppl. 55 (2009), pp. 0118–0123.
- [16] Leonard E Egede. “Major depression in individuals with chronic medical disorders: prevalence, correlates and association with health resource utilization, lost productivity and functional disability”. In: *General hospital psychiatry* 29.5 (2007), pp. 409–416.
- [17] Johan Sundström et al. “Prevalence, outcomes, and cost of chronic kidney disease in a contemporary population of 2· 4 million patients from 11 countries: The CaReMe CKD study”. In: *The Lancet Regional Health–Europe* 20 (2022).

- [18] Randall S Stafford and Philip L Cyr. “The impact of cancer on the physical function of the elderly and their utilization of health care”. In: *Cancer: Interdisciplinary International Journal of the American Cancer Society* 80.10 (1997), pp. 1973–1980.
- [19] Stephanie Mazzucca et al. “Expanding implementation research to prevent chronic diseases in community settings”. In: *Annual review of public health* 42.1 (2021), pp. 135–158.
- [20] Alarcos Cieza et al. “Global estimates of the need for rehabilitation based on the Global Burden of Disease study 2019: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019”. In: *The Lancet* 396.10267 (2020), pp. 2006–2017.
- [21] Axel Börsch-Supan et al. “Data resource profile: the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)”. In: *International journal of epidemiology* 42.4 (2013), pp. 992–1001.
- [22] Guido W Imbens. “Causal inference in the social sciences”. In: *Annual Review of Statistics and Its Application* 11 (2024).
- [23] Fabrizia Mealli. “Potential Outcomes”. In: *Encyclopedia of Quality of Life and Well-Being Research*. Springer, 2024, pp. 5362–5367.
- [24] Brantly Callaway and Pedro HC Sant’Anna. “Difference-in-differences with multiple time periods”. In: *Journal of econometrics* 225.2 (2021), pp. 200–230.
- [25] Anca Antoaneta Vărzaru. “Assessing the Relationships of Expenditure and Health Outcomes in Healthcare Systems: A System Design Approach”. In: *Healthcare*. Vol. 13. 4. MDPI. 2025, p. 352.
- [26] World Health Organization. *International Perspectives on Spinal Cord Injury*. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013. ISBN: 9789241564663. URL: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/international-perspectives-on-spinal-cord-injury>.
- [27] Monroe Berkowitz. *Spinal cord injury: an analysis of medical and social costs*. Demos Medical Publishing, 1998.